

STUDY ON THE FORMABILITY OF THERMOPLASTIC LAMINAR COMPOSITE DEPENDING ON THE TYPES OF FABRIC

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SUMMARY: 3-dimensional formability of the thermoplastic laminar composite was studied based on manufacturing conditions. Five different types of the plain weave fabric were used as reinforcement with PET film as matrix. The square blank was made first by press consolidation technique and then formed into the hemispheric shape. The B-factor as ratio of yarn width and distance between yarns was used as the criterion of formability for five types of plain weave fabric. The used forming rate was 100 mm/min and 300 mm/min. The B-factor of glass fabric for each blank thickness was 0.1, 0.3, 0.45, 0.55 and 0.7. The formability of PET/Glass fabric laminar composite was estimated in terms of forming rate with the thickness distribution, area ratio of the blank and inter-ply shear angle. The thickness distribution across hemisphere was strongly affected by the B-factor, forming rate and blank thickness. The area ratio of the blank was increased with the B-factor, forming rate and blank thickness. Also, it was found that the intra-ply shear angle depends on the B-factor and forming rate.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastic laminar composite, formability, thickness distribution, intra-ply shear angle

INTRODUCTION

Recently, fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites have been shown a potentiality that can be developed by the traditional sheet forming and other processing for manufacturing composites. In actual forming process, continuous fiber sheet does not allow the extensibility in fiber direction. The prominent phenomenon during forming is shown as the form of shear at 45° of fiber direction. But, the extensibility at fiber direction is possible in discontinuous system. If the length-to-diameter ratio of fiber is very high, its mechanical properties in solid phase can be equal to its properties of continuous system [1-3]. However, the matrix of composites becomes a liquid phase near the melting point, it is difficult to predict the material behavior. In addition to that, both stacking sequence and fiber direction affect as the factor of material behavior and its properties in multi-layers because the layers have an interaction between them. Even though the understanding of material behavior for composites is not enough, recent researches have shown much progress with applying new techniques to the traditional processes for composites. Laminar composites have some inevitable problems due to the wrinkling for the different geometric shaping, stacking sequence and material stiffness [4-5]. Even though the advantages of laminar fabric composites are not proved in terms of its elastic properties, their usage are increased these days due to many advantages such as low manufacturing cost, high fracture toughness and for thermodynamic properties and processing technique, etc. Polyethylene-Terephthalate (PET) has been used in the various engineering fields because of its excellent mechanical properties and low cost. PET can be high-functional composites that can be used in the many industrial fields. Generally, PET has some disadvantages in processing such as high processing temperature, narrow range of processing window and wide range of mechanical properties depending on molecular structure. Therefore, press consolidation technique with PET tape is applied as a processing technique for fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composite [6]. Plain weave fabric among many types of glass fiber is used as reinforcement. The sheet is formed in the shape of hemisphere to estimate 3-dimensional formability. Forming characteristics of used composite are studied as functions of the geometry of plain weave fabric, laminar thickness and forming rate.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of blank

Press consolidation technique was applied to make the square plank (300mm x 280mm) with thickness of 1.1mm and 1.5mm. Many tests were performed to find the optimum conditions for the manufacturing processes depending on temperature, pressure, vacuum and time at pre-heating unit and press. PET film (thickness=36μm) as matrix supplied by Toray Saehan Inc. and glass plain weave fabric (609, 612, 618,

635 and 650 types) as reinforcement supplied by Hankook Fiber Co. Ltd. in Korea were used respectively. The description for five types of plain weave fabric is listed in Table 1. As the count (yarn/in.) in warp and weft direction for 609, 635, 650 among five types is different. They were stacked by even numbers for all

Process	Pre-heating		Consolidation				Cooling
			Step I		Step II		
Unit	Pre-heating unit		Press				
Processing parameters	Heating temp. (°C)	Heating time (min)	Pressing time (sec)	Mold temp. (°C)	Pressing time (sec)	Pressing force (kN)	Cooling rate (°C/min)
	290	12	10	Upper: 140 Lower: 260	15	125	20

types of fabric to compare. Processing parameters at pre-heating, consolidation and cooling sections of press consolidation technique are listed in Table 2. They are the optimum conditions that acquired from the previous works [7]. The blank (160mm x 160mm) was cut by electric band saw from the square plank. The volume fraction of the blank was about 30% by volume. The blank was held under constant displacement under the blank holder without applying the pressure. The semi-consolidated composites of plate were formed in press after pre-heating for manufacturing of 3-dimensional products. The blank was deformed through the second consolidation in installed 3-dimensional mold at forming rate of 100 and 300mm/min and cooled in press. Fig. 1 is the schematic of equipment for hemispheric forming and they were designed to make a product with 1.3mm thickness. Also, the mold had a Teflon® PTFE coating for easy separation after forming of product.

Fig. 1 Schematic of equipment for hemispheric forming

Table 1. Description for plain weave fabric

Type	Count (Yarn/In.)		Weight (g/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)
	Warp	Weft		
609	20	10	54	0.09
612	18	18	132	0.12
618	18	18	197	0.18
635	17	14	337	0.35
650	10	8	529	0.50

Table 2. The used processing parameters for press consolidation technique

Evaluation of formability

The various parameters about formability and press consolidation technique to manufacture the thermoplastic composites were established. The formed products of 3-dimensional shape such as hemispheric shape were manufactured and the formability for plain weave fabric was investigated in various conditions by changing the fabric types, forming rate and blank thickness on manufacturing processes. 3-dimensional forming of fabric-reinforced composites depends on the thickness distribution of formed product or uniformity. The formability is judged by wrinkle and tear according to the degree of bending and draw-in or complexity of product shape. It is important to evaluate whether the thickness of whole product is distributed uniformly. Three good products that are axisymmetric among hemispheric products were selected by image analysis program (Image-Pro V3). And four specimens were chosen again among eight pieces that is each 1/8 division of whole hemispheric product. The data was the average

of twelve specimens. The thickness of formed specimen was measured by digital caliper (accuracy 1/100 mm) and the thickness distribution was evaluated. The projective area of the blank before and after forming, and the critical intra-ply shear angle at 45° of fiber direction were measured by image analysis program. To measure the critical intra-ply shear angle, the direction of fiber was visualized by melting PET at the measuring parts. The types of plain weave fabric as reinforcement were 609, 612, 618, 635 and 650 as shown in Fig. 2. The pattern of yarns was investigated as the factor that represents the characteristic of plain weave fabric. The ratio of the width of yarn (W_w) and distance between yarns (W_d) in warp direction was defined as “Band factor (B-factor)”. They are 0.1, 0.3, 0.45, 0.55 and 0.7 for 609, 612, 618, 635 and 650, respectively. As the B-factor is close to 1, it represents that there is no distance between yarns with increase of yarn width. The distributions of thickness and intra-ply shear angle were measured at each 16 parts per 5mm from center to 75mm in 0° and 45° directions as shown in Fig. 3. Thickness distribution was defined as $X = t_f / t_o$ where t_f is the thickness of 16 measuring parts from center to 75mm and t_o is the thickness of hemispheric center. The formability for thickness was estimated by standard deviation (S.d.(X)) of measured thickness distribution.

Fig. 2 Photograph of plain weave fabrics and definition of the B-factor

Fig. 3 Schematic of a quarter of hemisphere after forming

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thickness distribution

The semi-consolidated square blank was formed into the hemispheric shape. The thickness distribution after forming was examined for the blank thickness of 1.1mm and 1.5mm as functions of B-factor and forming rate. First, the blank thickness of 1.1 mm was estimated. The B-factor=0.7 was not evaluated because the blank thickness is at least 1.5mm. Fig. 4 shows the thickness distribution at measuring points from center to 75mm down. It is found that the degree of thickness variation is bigger as the B-factor increases. Standard deviation was applied for comparison to compensate these thickness changes. Fig. 5 represents standard deviation for the blank thickness of 1.1mm. The variation of thickness increases as the B-factor increases from 0.3 to 0.55, but it remains constant for the B-factor with 0.1 and 0.3. Also, the variation of thickness increases with forming rate. This phenomenon with B-factor=0.1 is a contrary result with anticipation that it can minimize wrinkles because the movement of yarn is the easiest during intra-ply shear deformation. Substantially, the blank with B-factor=0.1 was stacked with more numbers of glass fabrics than others. It was difficult that yarns with B-factor=0.1 were aligned in the directions of 0° and 90° because the width of yarn was narrow. Also, the thickness uniformity of this product was not so good. Standard deviation with measuring direction was bigger at 45° than at 0°. This is due to the interlocking phenomenon. At the beginning of forming, there was a shear deformation that prevents the wrinkle. At the end of forming, the wrinkle was formed by interlocking phenomenon that prevents fiber movement beyond the critical shear angle. Also, the difference between 0° and 45° is bigger as the B-factor increases.

The formability about the others except B-factor=0.1 was evaluated because the degree of thickness uniformity and arrangement fiber for B-factor=0.1 is not good as mentioned in results with the blank thickness of 1.1mm. As shown in Fig. 6, the values of standard deviation for the blank thickness of 1.5 mm decrease remarkably for all B-factors and forming rates which are quite different than the samples with 1.1mm thickness. Since the number of fabric increases to thicken the laminar thickness, the forming pressure becomes very high. And, due to the appeared intra-ply shear and inter-ply debonding during forming, arrangement of fiber is not equal to the early prepared blank. In this case, the formability will be the worst. Standard deviation decreases as the B-factor increases for the blank thickness of 1.5mm that is unlikely with 1.1mm thickness specimen. There was a small difference between 0° and 45° directions for the B-factor of 0.3 and 0.45. This is due to the increase of the number of glass fabric. As summarized the above results, it can be seen that thickness uniformity of 1.5mm was superior than specimen with 1.1mm as shown in Fig. 7. The trend for thickness of 1.1 and 1.5mm was opposite. This is due to the fact that the increase of fabric number made a forming pressure higher and showed a wrinkle by inter-ply debonding simultaneously.

Area ratio of blank

Fig. 4 Thickness distribution as a function of B-factor for 100mm/min of forming rate and the blank thickness of 1.1mm

Fig. 5 Standard deviation as functions of B-factor and forming rate for the blank thickness of 1.1mm

Fig. 6 Standard deviation as function of B-factor and forming rate for the blank thickness of 1.5mm

Fig. 7 Comparison of standard deviation between the blank thickness of 1.1mm and 1.5mm as functions of B-factor and forming rate

After molding hemispheric product with the square blank, a projected blank shape was investigated. The area ratio of the blank is defined as the ratio of projected area of hemispheric product after forming and area of the square blank before forming. Fig. 8 represents the area ratio of the blank for the blank thickness of 1.1mm. The value increased as the B-factor increased. This affect by forming rate became more sensitive as the B-factor increased. Fig. 9 represents the area ratio with 1.5mm of the blank thickness. That was nearly the same in the case of 1.1mm of the blank thickness. As compared the cases between 1.1 and 1.5mm of the blank thickness, the area ratio of the blank showed the increasing trend as the B-factor was larger and forming rate was faster as shown in Fig. 10.

Intra-ply shear angle

The intra-ply shear angle is an angle between warp and weft that was measured at 45°. Figs. 11-12 represent a shear angle from the center to fringe of hemispheric specimen for 1.5mm of the blank thickness. The trend was same for two forming rates, but the value for 100mm/min was bigger than that

Fig. 11 Shear angle as a function of B-factor for 100mm/min of forming rate and the blank thickness of 1.5mm

Fig. 12 Shear angle as a function of B-factor for 300mm/min of forming rate and the blank thickness of 1.5mm

Fig. 13 Maximum shear angle as functions of B-factor and forming rate for the blank thickness of 1.5mm

Fig. 14 Comparison of shear angle between the blank thickness of 1.1mm and 1.5mm as a function of B-factor

for 300mm/min. The shear angle increased as far away from the center of hemisphere. This value was bigger when the B-factor was small. The intra-ply shear angle had a maximum value at the fringe. As shown in Fig. 13, the maximum shear angle increased as the B-factor and forming rate decreased. The changing trend of shear angle for 100 and 300mm/min of forming rate was almost same. As related with area ratio of the blank, it can be found that the shear angle had an effect on the area ratio of the blank. The area ratio of the blank was bigger when the shear angle became smaller. Fig. 14 represents the comparison of intra-ply shear angle for 1.1 and 1.5mm of the blank thickness. There was a little difference for the blank thickness between 1.1 mm and 1.5mm. Therefore, the shear angle was strongly affected by the B-factor.

CONCLUSIONS

3-dimensional formability of the thermoplastic laminar composite was studied. From this study, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- 1) For the blank thickness of 1.1mm, the variation of thickness increased as the B-factor and forming rate increased. The difference in thickness was small as the B-factor decreased. Standard deviation with measuring direction was bigger at 45° than at 0°. The difference between the angles of 0° and 45° increased as both B-factor and forming rate decreased. For the 1.5mm sample, the standard deviation decreased remarkably for all B-factors that are opposite with 1.1mm sample. There was a small difference between 0° and 45° directions due to the increase in the number of glass fabric. The forming pressure was increased as the number of fabrics increased.
- 2) The area ratio of the blank increased as the B-factor, forming rate and blank thickness increased. The forming rate had a significant effect on the area ratio of the blank when the B-factor was large. Intra-ply shear angle increased when the yarn movement was big. The trend of shear angle from center to fringe was almost same for all forming rates. There was a little difference depending on the blank thickness. The value of shear angle was big when the B-factor is small. As related these results with area ratio of the blank, it can be found that the shear angle had a significant effect on the area ratio of the blank.

REFERENCES

1. Bersee H. E. N. and Beukers A., "Diaphragm forming of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics: influence of temperature, pressure and velocity on the forming Upilex-R® diaphragms", *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 33, 949-958, 2002.
2. Murtagh A. M. and Mallon P. J., "Shear characterization of unidirectional and fabric-reinforced thermoplastics composites for pressforming applications", *Proceedings of The 10th ICCM*, Whistler, Vancouver, 1995.
3. Lim T. C., Ramakrishna S. and Shang H. M., "Axisymmetric sheet forming of knitted fabric composite by combined stretch forming and deep drawing", *Composites Part B*, 30, 495-502, 1999.
4. Breuer U., Neitzel M., Ketzer V. and Reinicke R., "Deep drawing of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic: wrinkle formation and their reduction", *Polymer Composites*, 17(4), 643-647, 1996.
5. Nakamura Y. and Ohata T., "The effect of newly developed blank holder on press forming of glass-cloth reinforced thermoplastic sheet", *Key Engineering Materials*, 137, 40-46, 1998.
6. Andersent T. Logstrup, "Development of a rapid press consolidation technique for continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites", *Proceeding of 18th Riso International Symposium on Materials Science*, 237-244, 1997.
7. Lee D. J. and Shin I. J., "Effects of vacuum, mold temperature and cooling rate on mechanical properties of press consolidated glass fiber/PET composite", *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 33(8), 1107-1114, 2002.